

www.arseam.com

**International Journal of
Advances in Engineering
& Scientific Research**

Academic Research
IN SCIENCE, ENGINEERING, ART & MANAGEMENT

**International Journal of
Advances in Engineering &
Scientific Research
(IJAESR)**

ISSN: 2349 -3607 (Online)

ISSN: 2349 -4824 (Print)

Available online at:

<http://www.arseam.com/content/volume-1-issue-5-sep-2014>

Email: editor@arseam.com

Instructions for authors and subscription information:

<http://www.arseam.com/>

GREEN COMPUTING : THE FUTURE OF LIVELINESS

M.JENIFER

Assistant professor,

Department Of Computer Application and Software Systems
Sri Krishna Arts and Science College,Coimbatore-08, India.

S.G.NANDHINI, R.RANJITHA, M.CHITRA

Department Of Computer Application and Software Systems
Sri Krishna Arts and Science College, Coimbatore-08, India.

Abstract

This electronic document is a “live” template. The various components of your paper [green computing and its activities, virtualization] are already defined in this portrait on as illustrated by the portions given in this document.

Green computing is the process of designing, manufacturing and using computers and its components in a better way i.e. less harmful.

Keywords: component: green computing-green revolution-Software and deployment optimization-virtualization-telecommuting-data center power- Product longevity- Materials Recycling.

I. INTRODUCTION

Green computing is the process of designing the computer and its related products and manufacturing and using it would help natural resources and it reduces the harmfulness. The work of green computing includes the implementation of energy, efficient CPU, servers, etc.It also reduces resource consumption. It implements the habit of proper disposal of electronic waste (e-waste).

The initiatives introducing green computing in US was a labeling program called energy star which was conceived by the environmental protection agency (EPA) in 1992. In Europe and Asia many such program where adopted.

Need for Green Computing:

Green computing is must in a company to promote energy efficient computers. The following points are the effective needs for green computing;

- CLIMATE CHANGE: The research has concluded that CO2 and other gas emission causes global climate and environment damages. Preserving the planet will also preserve the life in earth.
- SAVINGS: Green computing leads to cost savings. Energy cost is been reduced from servers, cooling, and lightning for many corporations.
- RELIABILITY OF POWER: Energy supply is declining or flat. There is an efficient system maintained here which ensures the healthy power.
- COMPUTING: There is a critical point in computing power consumption. The data centers uses power and cooling due to high densities.

II. ACTIVITIES OF GREEN COMPUTING

The basis for green computing shows the plan of designers to make future computer more eco-friendly in its life span, from manufacture to recycling:

- Energy-intensive manufacturing of computer parts can be minimized and efficiency of energy consumption in the manufacturing process.
- Upgrading and repairing is easier and cheaper.
- Avoiding the discards controls the e-waste out of dumps and also saves energy and materials for a new computer.
- Green light displays made of OLEDs or organic light - emitting diodes replaces the Power-sucking displays.
- The lead can be replaced by silver and copper hence lead is a toxic material which is harmful.

III. GREEN COMPUTING GROUPS

There are many green computing groups but one of the popular one is TACTIAL INCREMENTALISTS. These groups uses green computing for only saving the cost rather than saving the environment. This green computing concept emerges naturally as businesses to compete effectively in the market. This is mainly for economic welfare and not for political pressure.

The leaders should take the social and environmental impacts of new emerging technologies. This should be made marketing and branding. Unlike the position in tactical incrementalists, the leaders should recognize the needful for it. This is an effort of making the IT personnel is responsible for managing and ensuring efficient and effective expenditures.

IV. GREEN REVOLUTION

An IT vendor applies the green standards to their own operations because:

- New revenue opportunities
- Fear of a customer backlash
- It works as a duplicate for a good patriotic corporate citizen.

The awareness programmers may include the following issues:

- Green computing usage minimizes energy devastation in an organizations

- The use of non toxic material is helpful in making the worker save from health problem and hazards.
- It saves the country's resource.

V. APPROACHES TO GREEN COMPUTING

The study and practice of designing ,manufacturing, using, and disposing of computers ,servers, and subsystems like monitors, printers, storage devices, and networking and communications systems – efficiently and effectively with minimal and no impact is the concept of green computing . There are fiscal motivations for companies to take control of their own power consumption:

“THE EFFICIENT AND POWERFUL AVAILABILITY OF MANAGEMENT TOOLS MIGHT STILL EXIST AS CRISP, SIMPLE, AND SENSABLE”.

Lets us see about its approaches;

A. Developing a Green Machine:

The power management features are being activated on the computer in order to save energy and money while helping the environment. There are two of the most effective ways for making the computer more environmentally friendly

- SLEEP MODE: Sleep or standby mode conserves energy by cutting off power to your display, hard drive, and peripherals. The computer switches from sleep mode by moving your mouse or pressing any key in keyboard and computer takes you back to its previous operating state. Sleep mode is an effective ways to conserve battery power in a laptop computer.
- HIBERNATE MODE: Hibernate mode saves energy and protects your work by copying system data to a reserved area on hard drive and the turning off the computer. It reduces the wear and tear on your computer. Be sure to set the system to automatically go to hibernate mode ant time if battery power a critically low level

B. Product longevity:

Gartner maintains the PC manufacturing process accounts for 70% for the natural resources. The biggest contribution to green computing is to prolong the equipment's lifetime. For example, manufacturing a new PC makes a greatest footprint than manufacturing a new RAM module to upgrade an existing one, thus the upgrade saves the user's purchase towards a new computer.

C. Software and deployment optimization

Algorithmic efficiency:

Algorithm efficiency has an impact on the computer resource for a given computing functions, if the algorithmic efficiency is doesn't have that much impact then it is an important consideration. By the study by a physicist, the average search released 7 grams of carbon dioxide (CO₂).however it is been arguing instead of a typical search produces 0.2 grams of CO₂ only.

Resource allocation

Algorithms can also be used to route data to data centers where electricity is less expensive. Researchers have tested an energy allocation algorithm which successfully routes the traffic to the location that cheapest the energy costs. The researchers make the project up to a 40 percent savings on energy costs. Mainly on idea this approach doesn't reduces the amount of energy to be used.

Larger server centers are available located where energy and land are inexpensive. The available renewable energy and climate is used for cooling or locating them. The heat caused is used for other purposes in green sitting decisions.

D. Virtualization

Virtualization helps in the by organizations to consolidate their servers onto fewer pieces of hardware, which results in savings.

For example, instead of having one computer for each service, a set of services can be established in a server for a larger virtualized system. This benefit in several ways:

- a) The total amount of hardware used in your environment is being reduced.
- b) Power of the Idle Virtual servers.
- c) Much less idle time is been in virtualized servers and it is waste less.
- d) Reduction in space allocation, renting, air.
- e) For conversion to virtualized systems, some companies pays the rebates.
- f) Increases in a server group's ability to share resources in because of virtualization.
- g) Increased up to 80% as opposed to an initial 10-15%, It is the Server utilization rates.

(Fig 3: Virtualization : The key to Green Computing)

Data center power:

Data centers, which have been criticized because of the primary focus for proponents of green computing is its extraordinary high energy demand. The federal government has set a minimum 10% reduction target for data center energy usage by 2011 on the principle of the aid of a self-styled ultra efficient evaporative cooling technology, **for instance: Google Inc. has been able to reduce its energy consumption to 50% of that of the industry average.**

A data center consumes the power which can be used to power thousands of homes. it makes data centers for more energy efficient.

Operating system support:

Many operating systems are engaged in the process of green computing:

- Process like operating system timers, processor power management and display panel brightness requires more efficiency, which is refined and provided by Windows 7
- Linux Os utilizing fewer resources than other Os, and also have a better power management facility.

The desktop operating system like Microsoft Windows has the process of consuming less PC power management features since Windows 95 which initially provides for (suspend-to-RAM) stand-up and a monitor low power state. Many the significant of these operating systems are to reduce the power management system. The setting is more advanced with multiple power plans, scheduled power, anti-insomnia, enterprise power usage reporting etc. Windows 2000 was the first NT based operating system to include power management. Windows 2000 introduced a Group Policy i.e., the technology which allowed administrators to centrally configure most Windows features.

Power supply:

The power supply is the major factor in green computing. Basically, desktop computer power supplies (PSUs) 70–75% efficient, the remaining energy goes as heat. An industry initially uses 80% of power supply efficiently, with the help of this efficient power supply the above models typically replaces the older PSU's of the factory. From July 20, 2007, it is certified that the desktop PSUs must have atleast 80% efficient.

Storage:

The storage is in a smaller form factor e.g. 2.5 inch. The hard disk drives consume less power per gigabyte often than physically larger drives but solid-state drives store data in DRAM or flash memory. Low capacity flash based devices without moving parts consumes less power.

Introducing the MySpace: The MySpace is a storage available which was able to permanently retire several of their servers i.e. MySpace data centers by 80%, by which carbon footprint is further reduced with the high speed performance of heavy -load servers.

Video card:

A fast GPU only consumes the largest power consumer in a computer. It is meant for energy efficient display thus, the option includes:

- No video card is used.(a terminal source of sharing, shared clients, desktop sharing software is required for display)
- Motherboard video output is used which is typically low 3D performance and low power.
- Based on low idle power we should select a GPU which has an average wattage or performance per watt.

Display:

CRT (Cathode-Ray Tube) monitors are typically used for more power than LCD monitors. CRTs (Cathode Ray Tube) are vacuum tubes that use electron guns and fluorescent screens to display images. They also contain lead in a sufficient amount. LCD monitors typically use a cold-cathode fluorescent bulb to provide light for the display. Light emitting diodes are used in some places instead of fluorescent bulb to reduce the cost. Fluorescent light contains mercury where LED lights don't.

E. Telecommuting:

The green computing implements teleconferencing and telepresence technologies. The advantages are many; worker satisfaction is increased, reduction of greenhouse gas emissions and increased profit margins, heat, lighting etc. It brings cost efficiency and also prevents from the emission of CO₂. Voice over IP (VoIP) reduces the telephony wiring infrastructure by sharing the existing Ethernet copper which is a toxic metal. Hot desk making includes VoIP and phone extension mobility makes it much easier and practical.

F. Materials Recycling:

The computing equipment is being recycled to keep the harmful materials such as lead, mercury, and chromium out of landfills, but often computers gathered through recycling drives where environmental standards are less strict thus, Silicon Valley Toxics Coalition says that 80% of the post-consumer e-waste is being collected for recycling is shipped from abroad to countries such as China, India, and Pakistan, so only computing in our countries supplies only some materials, such as printer cartridges, paper, and batteries may be recycled as well.

VI. ADVANTAGES

- Energy usage is reduced from green computing technique which translates into lower carbon dioxide emissions.
- There is also reduction in the process of power plant and transportation where fossil fuel is used.
- Lesser amount of energy is involved in green computing.
- The energy explored in green computing is eco-friendly.
- Energy, resource is being saved in green computing, where it also saves money.
- The concept of green computing changes the government policy to the process of recycling and lower use of energy by individuals and businesses.
- It reduces the harmful risks from laptops such as chemicals that cause cancer, nerve damage and immune reactions in humans.

VII. DISADVANTAGES

- Green computing is quite costly.
- Green computers are underpowered.
- Rapid technology had a great change.

REFERENCES

- ✚ <http://searchdatacenter.techtarget.com/definition/green-computing>
- ✚ <http://www.tech-faq.com/green-computing.html>
- ✚ http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Green_computing
- ✚ <http://www.ncomputing.com/company/green-computing>